

Research Data Policy

for the project *The impacts of ocean fine-scale whirls on climate and ecosystems* (in short: WHIRLS) funded under the European Research Council (ERC) within HORIZON ERC Synergy Grants (Grant agreement ID: 101118693; DOI:[10.3030/101118693](https://doi.org/10.3030/101118693))

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The project partners of the research project *WHIRLS* [1] declare the following Research Data Policy in accordance with the *WHIRLS* scientific steering committee, the central data management staff and with the legal obligation under Horizon Europe [2] and the EU's open science policy [3]. Please note that this document is not legally binding but reflects the high ambitions of all project partners and contributors within *WHIRLS* to transparently share and publish all research output in long-term repositories for international re-use.

Basic rules

The *WHIRLS* partners and contributors are committed to handle generated scientific data according to the FAIR Data Principles (Findable – Accessible – Interoperable – Reusable) [4] and the Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice [5].

Newly collected data within the framework of *WHIRLS* will be shared transparently and published in long-term repositories for international re-use. Quality control of data as well as workflows for delivery of metadata and data from observation/collection to archiving and publishing will be handled within the partner institutions. These workflows and procedures are documented in the Data Management Plan (DMP) and supported by the data management staff.

Data responsibilities

The central data management collaborates tightly with the responsible data management of the partner institutions, which, in turn, have direct contact to the individual scientists. The data management provides support and advice regarding, e.g. harmonization and standardization, archival, integration and documentation of data and metadata. With this the data management provides advice to the scientists within their specific discipline on how to make data FAIR and reproducible.

Data exchange

Within the funding period of *WHIRLS*, metadata will be collected and shared by scientists including links to repositories and information on the contact person via an appropriate documentation portal, for example the information system OSIS [6] at GEOMAR, thus enabling data sharing among all partners. These metadata shall be made available without undue delay. Unpublished research data are under no circumstances disclosed or shared outside of *WHIRLS*, without consultation and permission of the author or responsible contact person (see Appendix A: “*Agreement to receive unpublished data licensed under the WHIRLS Research Data Policy*”)

Data publication

Data publication of all datasets should be realised at latest 1 year after collection/generation and calibration/validation were completed. Exceptions of the 1-year regulation can be granted by the *WHIRLS* scientific steering committee on request of the person responsible for the data. All collected data together with standard metadata (minimum DataCite Mandatory Properties [7]) should be archived and published in suitable, sustainably operated, trustworthy long-term repositories, such as WDCC [8], PANGAEA [9], SEANOE [10], SND [11] or Zenodo [12].

In terms of the Open Access policy, unnecessary restrictions on the availability of research data should be minimised (“Open by default”). Appropriate time limits for data embargoes must be documented in the DMP.

For all kinds of publications, it is mandatory to acknowledge EU support through a funding statement, display of the EU emblem and the ERC logo [13]:

'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe ERC Synergy Grant programme under grant agreement No 101118693 – WHIRLS (DOI:[10.3030/101118693](https://doi.org/10.3030/101118693)). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.'

Research data should be published under the CC BY license using the most open CC BY 4.0 license [14], while metadata are generally shared under the CC0 1.0 license [15]. Persistent identifiers such as handle [16] or DOI [17] for data sets, ROR [18] for affiliations and ORCID [19] for authors are promoted by the data managers and used wherever possible.

Data visibility

Publication in appropriate data repositories will also ensure the findability in data portals such as the Helmholtz DataHub [20], EMODnet [21] and hence increase the visibility and value of the data.

Appendix A

Agreement to receive unpublished data licensed under the *WHIRLS* Research Data Policy

I will receive a copy of the following unpublished data set(s) [if no PID is available please specify in detail experiment/simulation name and parameters, temporal and spatial range]

.....

from

I agree to the provisions stipulated in the *WHIRLS* Research Data Policy (v1.0) and the following common principle:

"If unpublished data of the project is used for a publication, conference contribution and/or public meeting, the provided citation of the data set is mandatory to be included as well as co-authorship for resulting publications has to be offered to the data provider(s) including a funding statement in the acknowledgment such as *'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe ERC Synergy Grant programme under grant agreement No 101118693 – WHIRLS (DOI:[10.3030/101118693](https://doi.org/10.3030/101118693))*.

Furthermore, I will not distribute this unpublished data set or parts of it."

Name:

Affiliation and Address:

E-mail Address:

Date and Signature of the receiver of the data set:

References

- [1] WHIRLS – ERC Fact sheet, available from [doi:10.3030/101118693](https://doi.org/10.3030/101118693)
- [2] Open science in Horizon Europe; https://rea.ec.europa.eu/open-science_en - open-science-in-horizon-europe
- [3] The EU's open science policy; https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en - the-eus-open-science-policy
- [4] Wilkinson, M.D., et al. (2016): The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3: 160018. [doi:10.1038/sdata.2016.18](https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18)
- [5] Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (2019). Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice. Code of Conduct. [doi:10.5281/zenodo.3923602](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3923602)
- [6] Ocean Science Information System (OSIS) [Software]. GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel; <https://osis.geomar.de>
- [7] DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2024). DataCite Metadata Schema for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs. Version 4.5. DataCite e.V. [doi:10.14454/g8e5-6293](https://doi.org/10.14454/g8e5-6293)
- [8] World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) Data Publisher for Earth System model data. German Climate Computing Center, Hamburg; <https://www.wdc-climate.de>
- [9] PANGAEA Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science. Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research (AWI); <https://pangaea.de>
- [10] Sea Scientific Open Data Publication (SEANOE); <https://www.seanoe.org>
- [11] Swedish National Data Service (SND); <https://snd.se/en>
- [12] Zenodo. CERN Data Centre & Invenio <https://zenodo.org>
- [13] The EU's ERC logos for funding statement; <https://erc.europa.eu/support/logos>
- [14] Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0). Creative Commons; <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>
- [15] CC0 1.0 Universal license (CC0 1.0) Public Domain Dedication. Creative Commons; <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/deed.en>
- [16] ePIC – Persistent Identifiers for eResearch; <https://www.pidconsortium.net>
- [17] Digital Object Identifier (DOI). International DOI Foundation; <https://www.doi.org>
- [18] Research Organization Registry (ROR). Collaborative ROR Initiative; <https://ror.org>
- [19] Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID). ORCID, Inc.; <https://orcid.org>
- [20] Helmholtz DataHub: Research Field Earth and Environment. Helmholtz Centre Potsdam - German Research Centre for Geosciences (GFZ); <https://datahub.erde-und-umwelt.de>
- [21] The European Commission (EC) *in situ* marine data service: European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet); <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu>